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WORKING TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION DESIGN APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents differing points of view surrounding consumption patterns in relation to sustainable development and how design can support lifestyle changes. The potential for designers to incite change is discussed, along with the following conflicting consumption theories in relation to design: consuming less vs. consuming efficiently, policy vs. consumer choice, status-seeking goods vs. symbolism in identity and trend vs. longevity. Two companies: TOMS Shoes and SIGG are examined within the context of these theories. Understanding conflicting ideas surrounding sustainable consumption may help designers develop a more balanced vision for the future and invoke change through design.

Keywords: sustainability, consumption, conflicting theories

INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation and social inequity are a growing concern in today's society and it is evident that our current, unsustainable consumption patterns are contributing to the problem (Thorpe, 2007). The term "sustainable" implies longevity and denotes a process that has the capacity to maintain and support itself over a long period of time (Thorpe, 2007). Sustainability applies to both environmental and social well-being.

Many studies, such as the Club of Rome's seminal Limits to Growth, published in 1972, argue that the rate at which we are consuming natural resources is unsustainable (Margolin, 2007). Our society is consuming these resources faster than they can be regenerated and we are releasing more waste into nature than it is capable of absorbing and processing

(Thorpe, 2007). In addition, our consumption patterns are contributing to the growing disparity between the wealthiest and poorest nations (Thorpe, 2007). As the world is becoming increasingly aware of the damaging nature of our actions and their implications for the future, it is clear that we must curb the rapid deterioration of our environment by creating sustainable solutions (Jackson, 2006). Design can play a key role in sustainable development and changing the patterns of consumption, not only in terms of resource consumption, but also in terms of the social issue of modifying behaviours.

This paper addresses the challenge of changing consumption patterns in relation to sustainable development and how design can support these changes. Theories concerning consumption and consumer behaviour are essential to gaining an understanding of sustainable consumption. These theories are heavily informed by psychology and sociology and are wrought with debate; their arguments about how change can and should be brought about are often fundamentally conflicting. As the topic of sustainable consumption is extremely broad, this paper offers a brief and very limited view of the issues. Many issues, such as life cycle analysis, materials, government policy and corporate responsibility are significant topics in themselves and require in-depth research to understand them comprehensively. However, this paper aims to contribute to the debates surrounding sustainable design and consumption by shedding light on a variety of perspectives and creating a broader understanding of the related challenges. This paper creates a theoretical framework for critiquing research on sustainable design, which is then applied to the analysis of two companies' products, as presented online.

This paper discusses the potential of designers to incite change and describes the following conflicting theories of consumption in relation to design: consuming less vs. consuming efficiently, policy vs. consumer choice, status-seeking goods vs. symbolism in identity and fashion vs. longevity. In this paper, two companies are examined: TOMS Shoes and SIGG and they are examined within the context of the theories discussed. The issue of sustainable consumption is entrenched in debate and disparate points of view, but a critical understanding of these ideas may help designers develop a more balanced vision for the future.

DESIGNER APATHY VS. AWARENESS & ACTION

Designers often avoid acknowledging the dilemma intrinsically enmeshed with their practice: creating new products also creates future waste (Brody, 2009). Advances in technology and knowledge can help designers create more sustainable solutions, yet designers have been slow to adopt these tools (Brody, 2009). Papanek (1995) argues that the majority of designers today, are not comfortable considering social responsibility in relation to goods they design. Since the Industrial Revolution, designers have been using the 'cradle to grave' life cycle model to produce mass amounts of commodities that are designed to be thrown away (McDonough & Braungart, 2009). "In fact, many products are designed with 'built-in obsolescence', to last only for a certain period of time, to allow - to encourage - the customer to get rid of the thing and buy a new model" (McDonough & Branart, 2009). McDonough & Branart (2009) argue that the 'cradle to grave' life cycle is a leading cause of our environmental problems and that a 'cradle to cradle' model must replace it, requiring a paradigm shift in the industrial agenda. The 'cradle to cradle' life cycle model focuses on reuse and design that considers a product's entire life cycle.

Papanek (1995) believes that designers can lead the way to a more sustainable future by employing life cycle assessment in their design process and making informed choices. Life cycle assessment involves critically analyzing every stage of a product's lifecycle and using this analysis to minimize ecological harm (Papanek, 1995). Life cycle analysis

takes into account six critical stages of a product's life: choice of materials, manufacturing processes, packaging, the finished product, transportation and disposal of the product (Papanek, 1995). Many believe that designers today have the ethical responsibility to proactively make sustainable design choices and include sustainability issues in design briefs for clients, even when they are not requested (Lorenz, 2009). Designers must rethink their role in society; they must be aware of changes that are taking place in sustainable design and understand how their practice can orient progress towards sustainable change (Manzini, 2009). Designers must see themselves as visionaries and future builders, as promoters of new business models and catalysers of change (Manzini, 2009). While there are many sustainable changes designers can make to their design processes, what role can designers play in affecting consumers' purchasing behaviours?

CONSUMING LESS VS. CONSUMING EFFICIENTLY

One of the major debates in sustainable consumption is between two arguments on the course human progress should take. One argument is that we need to significantly reduce our consumption rates by making lifestyle changes and the other is that we can maintain our current rate of consumption as long as we make products more efficient and sustainable (Jackson, 2006). The idea that we must consume less in order to function as a sustainable society emphasizes questioning and altering our attitude towards design, thus changing consumer behaviours, values, expectations and lifestyles (Jackson, 2006). This view suggests that we could live healthier, more fulfilling lives and reduce our impact on the environment by drastically cutting down on our consumption of material goods (Jackson, 2006). Papanek (1995) believes that our society's motto should be 'use less'. Businesses and designers tend to be afraid of this idea, because to them, it implies that if fewer products are purchased, less profit will be made (Papanek, 1995). However, Papanek (1995) argues that a shift to decreased consumption of goods goes along with a shift in the quality of design; products should be designed to last longer and will therefore cost more.

On the other hand, the idea of consuming less is criticized by some as being too ideological and value laden and too difficult to implement by means of policy (Jackson, 2006). The call to reduce consumption can be interpreted as being excessively judgmental of the way modern society functions, demonizing consumers and accusing them of being overly materialistic (Jackson, 2006). Controlling consumers' behaviour challenges their right to choose what they purchase, a topic that will be discussed in the next section. The argument to buy less undermines the role consumerism and design innovation play in economic growth (Jackson, 2006). Critics argue that proposals to reduce consumption patterns are simplistic and that it is naïve to believe that it can be done while maintaining economic growth (Jackson, 2006). However, critique of the 'use less' approach is not meant to be a pro-capitalist stance; "It is a genuinely progressive attempt to place social issues... at the heart of the consumption debate and promote an empathetic understanding of the social dilemmas faced by the modern consumer" (Jackson, 2006).

The opposing point of view asserts that sustainable consumption implies consuming more responsibly, not consuming decidedly less. The majority of institutions are opting for this position, placing emphasis on improving production processes and supplying the public with more environmentally friendly products and services.

...this institutional view is one in which sustainable consumption means (more) consumption of more sustainable products. This is to be achieved primarily through improvements in the efficiency with which resources are converted into economic goods (Jackson, 2006).

Rising consumption is welcomed here as an indication of rising living standards in society. However, it is asserted that business models must be revised to produce goods and services that are designed to be ecologically friendly (Jackson, 2006).

Critics of the 'consume efficiently' point of view, argue that this view obscures the scale of resource consumption patterns (Jackson, 2006). If a growing number of 'green' consumers purchase more and more 'sustainable' products, the scale of resource consumption is, in effect, continuing to grow, as are

the associated environmental impacts (Jackson, 2006). Thus, improvements in sustainable design are often counteracted by increases in scale.

POLICY VS. CONSUMER CHOICE

Policy makers realize that sustainable development relies heavily on them, but the debate lies in how much control they should assert over consumer's choices (Jackson, 2006). Policy relating to sustainable design affects the kinds of products designers can create. Changing the kinds of products offered in the marketplace, in effect, has the potential to change people's behaviours and lifestyles. Lifestyle change is becoming a key goal for environmental and social policy while national strategies pertaining to sustainable production are being developed in various countries across the world (Jackson, 2006). The major question for those wishing to instill change is how to encourage and persuade people to change their behaviours and adopt more environmentally and socially responsible habits (Jackson, 2006). Should specific changes become mandatory or should the choice remain up to the consumer?

One perspective is that consumers reserve the right to choose which products they buy because they have 'sovereignty' over these purchases. Consumers play a part in determining the kinds of products supplied, through their 'dollar votes'; therefore, they should reserve the right to choose which goods they purchase (Thorpe, 2010). The public should be free to make their own decisions and buy products that represent their values, tastes and personal preferences (Thorpe, 2010). Conversely, consumers can be seen as being

... 'locked-in' to a process of unsustainable consumption over which they have very little individual control. This perspective identifies a vital role for government shifting the institutional architecture of consumer 'lock-in' (Jackson, 2006).

This view sees consumer society as confined into an unhealthy lifestyle in which people are pressured into a cycle of constant consumption driven by social norms, habits, marketing and advertising (Jackson, 2006). In light of these issues, the challenge for environmental policy, as well as businesses, is 'choice editing'; meeting consumer demands while

supplying more environmentally friendly goods and steering society towards lifestyle changes (Thorpe, 2010). Businesses and the government must edit out unsustainable choices, making sustainable options the norm (Thorpe, 2010).

The issue of choice comes down to design as the main problem (Thorpe, 2010). Unsustainably designed products are the 'default', while sustainable options are considered the exception. Designers that are concerned with sustainability, redesign products to be ecologically friendly with the hopes that individuals will make the informed choice to purchase them over unsustainable products (Thorpe, 2010). Sustainable products often display environmental information, thus enabling consumers to make more knowledgeable purchasing decisions (Thorpe, 2010). The struggle to make sustainable design the norm, points to the role of designers as catalysts for systemic change. "There is an emerging demand for sustainable solutions. This includes product and service systems that propose different ways of being and doing from those currently dominant" (Manzini, 2009). Whether or not government policy controls sustainable product options, the more sustainable products designers produce and the more information they supply to the public, the greater the opportunity for consumers to make informed decisions and support sustainability.

STATUS-SEEKING GOODS VS. SYMBOLISM IN IDENTITY

Our consumption patterns and relationship to material goods reveal a lot about the nature of our society. Besides satisfying functional needs, designed objects play a significant role in the construction of identity, the pursuit of social status, social and/or sexual selection, the maintenance of social cohesion and the quest for personal and collective meaning (Jackson, 2006). This explains why we continue to pursue material consumption, even though it fails to satisfy us emotionally (Jackson, 2006). Theories in psychology suggest that consumer behaviour is partially shaped by social competition, leading to flaunting and status-seeking behaviours (Jackson, 2006). 'Positional goods' have the ability to situate us within a community, leading us to compare ourselves to our peers (Hirsch, 2006). They also

create false needs, making us feel that in order to be happy and create a certain perception of ourselves, we require specific possessions (Hirsch, 2006, pp). This type of comparative, competitive consumption leads to the erosion of meaningful social ties and increasingly commoditized lives (Hirsch, 2006). According to this theory, we are constantly striving to keep up with our 'competitors', who are also striving to position themselves through material consumption, thus engaging us in a race we can never win.

The idea of status-seeking consumer behaviour has been recently criticized, suggesting that it is overemphasized and that every-day purchases are not usually related to social positioning (Jackson, 2006). Quotidian purchases are usually made according to functional needs, convenience, habit and the effects of social norms on us as individuals (Jackson, 2006).

Drawing on theories from semiotics and anthropology, the symbols attached to designed objects are also significant in constructing our individual identities (Jackson, 2006). This idea applies to identity construction in a broader sense than status-seeking behaviours, and focuses on the symbolic significance of material goods. The products we purchase send signals about our values, lifestyles and social standing to others; we value these items for what they represent to us and to those around us (Jackson, 2006). For example, ownership of a specific type of car sends signals to others about the income, social standing, values and lifestyle of the owner. According to Jackson (2006), the symbols attached to material possessions help us construct and maintain our personal identities, helping us define ourselves to ourselves and to others. "Goods also communicate belongingness, affiliation, group identity, allegiance to particular ideals, distance from other ideals" (Jackson, 2006).

At this point in time, the kinds of design we choose to surround ourselves with, play a significant psychological and social role in our lives, in terms of identity, making it clear that forgoing these goods would be an extremely difficult task to accomplish. According to some, resisting consumption is not a

realistic solution to our environmental problems and it would leave a void in our lives, which we would have to learn to fill in other ways (Jackson, 2006).

FASHION VS. LONGEVITY

Conflicting theories arise when considering the roles of fashionable design and long lasting design in shifting consumption patterns towards sustainability. The idea behind designing for longevity relates to the concept of consuming less. Designers can play a part in remedying the nature of our throw-away culture based on the ‘cradle to grave’ design model, by creating longer lasting products (McDonough & Braungart, 2009). There is a need for designers to create solutions beyond aesthetics and responses to trends and to “... consider the emotional aspects involved in creating long-lasting appeal and physical aspects of durability” (Lorenz, 2009). Lorenz (2009) argues that designers must include reparability and emotional attachment in their design criteria, so that consumers wish to keep their purchases as long as possible and are not easily tempted to dispose of them for newer, trendier items. Fashion in design can negatively affect our society’s values, focusing on materialism as a way to achieve happiness (Walker, 2006). Papanek (1995) believes that a better understanding of the relationship between design and the Earth’s resources should lead to an emphasis on quality and permanence in design. Designers and manufacturers must question the ultimate environmental impact of what they create and design products that age gracefully and transcend trends and fads (Papanek, 1995). These considerations can lead to innovative solutions on the part of designers, as well reduced consumption behaviours on the part of consumers.

On the other hand, many companies and designers believe that fashion and style are extremely important to popularizing sustainable products. Reworking the appearance of products promotes sales in an already abundant market and creates interest in specific items over others (Walker, 2006). Fashion seems to oppose the fundamentals of sustainability, but in fact, it can contribute greatly towards shifting to more sustainable lifestyles (Walker, 2006). Style fosters creativity, energy and excitement in design, catching the public’s attention

and providing them with a sense of pleasure (Walker, 2006). Fashionable design solutions give companies a competitive edge and increase sales. Walker (2006) argues that fashion encourages innovation and without innovation, economic, technological and social stagnation can occur, leading to outmoded technologies, which can have harmful effects on the environment. Thus, fashion can help market sustainable products to consumers, potentially leading to more informed choices, while helping to spur innovation and development of sustainable design solutions.

BALANCING OUR VIEWS ON SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION

In order to develop a more balanced, complex understanding of the requirements for sustainable consumption, we must look beyond moralistic critiques of consumerism to find realistic design solutions. It is crucial to find a strategy for developing sustainable design and getting the public to accept it, and this strategy must operate in the mainstream, not purely at the margins of society as a radical “alternative lifestyle” (Jackson, 2006). Hobson (2006) speculates that most people are not concerned about sustainability because the “rationalization” of lifestyles tends to alienate them. This view claims that consumers will have to become knowledgeable about toxic materials and emissions related to product lifecycles and shape their lifestyles according to this logic, as part of an ecological paradigm shift (Hobson, 2006). Hobson (2006) argues that such an extreme view disregards the social concerns in peoples’ lives, thus negatively affecting the goal of sustainable development (Hobson, 2006). In order to work towards significant change, we must find a way to negotiate opposing theories and have them meet, in order to find the “right intensity of consumerism in our lives” (Thorpe, 2010). Designers may use the strengths from different viewpoints to propel them towards creating effective design solutions and consider sustainable design within the broader context of our society and culture. A balanced approach must embrace social well-being, environmental awareness and economic viability via incorporation of fashion into design (Walker, 2006). Sustainable design must

allow consumers to cultivate individualism and cultural meanings.

It remains a very real possibility that we could collectively devise a society in which it is possible to live better... in which the riches of one section of the population do not contribute to the poverty of the rest; in which improving our own quality of life is not achieved at the expense of those living in the future; and in which learning to live within these limits allows us to become, in some sense, more human” (Jackson, 2006).

Many organizations and businesses are in the process of implementing their visions of sustainability and alternative ways of consuming. The next section of this paper will discuss two unique companies and examine how they utilize design to promote sustainable consumption.

TOMS SHOES

TOMS Shoes is a company that has gained considerable success over the past few years, while identifying its business model as being based on sustainability and social responsibility. TOMS Shoes was founded in 2006, when American traveller Blake Mycoskie, visited Argentina and noticed that many of the children did not own shoes (TOMS Shoes, 2010). Mycoskie was inspired to help these children, so he used his entrepreneurial background to create TOMS Shoes, a shoe company that for every pair of shoes purchased, donates a pair of shoes to a child in need (TOMS Shoes, 2010). Later that year, Mycoskie returned to Argentina with 10,000 pair of shoes for donation, matching the 10,000 pairs of shoes the company had sold (TOMS Shoes, 2010). As of September 2010, TOMS has donated over one million pairs of shoes to children in need around the world (TOMS Shoes, 2010).

Mycoskie (2010) learned that children in many developing countries, often grow up walking barefoot and he recognized the functional importance of footwear. Soil-transmitted diseases are a major problem in developing countries and wearing shoes also protects the feet from getting cuts and infections (TOMS Shoes, 2010). Often times, children cannot attend school if they are barefoot, which prevents them from receiving an education and improving their quality of life in that respect (TOMS

Shoes, 2010). These are the reasons for TOMS’ “One for One” initiative.

The TOMS Shoes slogan “One for One” represents their unique, socially responsible business model. TOMS uses the purchasing power of consumers to transform them into benefactors, allowing the business to function sustainably, rather than depending on monetary support from fundraising (TOMS Shoes, 2010). This kind of sustainability allows TOMS to function as a business and as a charity at the same time, one feeding the other, so that the business model can sustain itself. TOMS is a for-profit business with a mandate of explicitly improving the well-being of others (TOMS Shoes, 2010). The company’s name also represents a vision for change; “TOMS” is derived from company’s previous name, “Shoes for Tomorrow” (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). The idea of ‘consuming efficiently’ applies to TOMS Shoes, as it encourages consumers to purchase material goods, but also gives them a sense of power, enabling them to easily contribute to a good cause.

In addition to the “One for One” initiative, TOMS shoes are designed with sustainability in mind. The shoes are modeled after the Argentinean alpargata, a type of shoe traditionally worn by farmers. Alpargatas are lightweight, dry quickly and are relatively inexpensive (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). Alpargatas were regaining popularity among young Argentinians, so Mycoskie got the idea to bring this style of shoe to North America (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). Mycoskie began by making the shoes himself, but without a shoe design background, they were not very comfortable (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). Mycoskie then hired professional shoe designers to improve the quality and comfort of the shoes (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008).

TOMS shoes are made of canvas with a EVA rubber composite sole, making them an exceptionally lightweight redesign of the original alpargata style. Mycoskie (2008) claims that TOMS shoes are environmentally friendly, but does not elaborate on details of this statement in relation to the original shoe model. The lack of online information about the materials of original TOMS shoes represents a gap in

the online information available to customers. This discrepancy highlights the potential disconnect between marketing claims and publicly available information, as well as the importance of transparency. However, Mycoskie does discuss the eco, vegan shoe model designed in collaboration with Whole Foods. The material that vegan TOMS (see figure 1) are made of is a blend of organic canvas and post-consumer recycled plastics; a material that is durable and long-lasting and also has low impact on the environment (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). As the brand produces mainly one style of shoe, its aim is to develop it into an iconic silhouette, such as Converse or Vans but TOMS is also designing other styles of the shoe in order to offer variety and reach a broader customer base (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008).

Figure 1. TOMS vegan Earthwise Slate Women's Classics (TOMS Shoes, 2010)

TOMS shoes are currently manufactured in Argentina, Brazil, Ethiopia and Asia and are sold in eight countries (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). TOMS manufacturing practices make it evident that the company does not employ life cycle assessment, as shipping shoes across the world contributes to pollution by the burning of fossil fuels (Papanek, 1995). Mycoskie (2008) explains that TOMS abides by production standards and fair labor practices in its factories, hiring a consulting group to help monitor factories and perform unannounced audits. Manufacturing of the shoes appears to abide by Papanek's (1995) 'manufacturing processes' stage of lifecycle assessment. However, Mycoskie's (2008) explanation of manufacturing is limited and does not

present a detailed picture of these processes, which leaves further transparency to be desired.

TOMS shoes has been able to achieve its success solely by word of mouth, without any use of advertising or traditional marketing (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). The shoes' popularity may be partly due to design and partly due to the symbolism attached to the brand. Consumers who choose to purchase and wear TOMS, in effect, are indicating their beliefs and values to others around them. Wearing TOMS may even help consumers construct and maintain their identity; if an individual wishes to become a more ethical consumer, purchasing these shoes may instill a sense of power in him/her and could inspire the individual to take more control of his/her consumption patterns. However, the gaining popularity and symbolism attached to TOMS, may nudge it into 'status-seeking' territory, as the shoes are aesthetically distinct and easily identifiable. People may purchase TOMS simply because they are fashionable or in order to portray themselves as being concerned with sustainability and social equity. These customers may be completely uninterested in making lifestyle changes that go beyond consumption of material goods; as such changes require a considerable amount of knowledge and effort.

On the other hand, some customers have told Mycoskie (2008) that they wear TOMS because of the cause behind them, even though they dislike the aesthetic of the shoe. Wearing shoes for such a reason indicates the power of symbolism behind them, as these customers could just have easily donated the same amount of money to a charitable organization. Customers that wear TOMS even though they find them 'ugly' are displaying their values by means of fashion choices. Is this a bad thing? Regardless of the conscious or subconscious reasons behind purchasing TOMS Shoes, the fact remains that it is harnessing purchasing power to benefit the greater good in order to make a positive impact on the world. Making informed choices about their purchasing habits, is one way for people to work towards sustainable consumption, but the example of TOMS Shoes shows that companies can utilize sustainable design to affect peoples' purchases.

TOMS has also developed beyond being a shoe brand and has become a movement, in a sense. As a company, it is attempting to expand the public's awareness of social responsibility and empower them to take action. TOMS has created the 'One Day Without Shoes' campaign, Campus Clubs and Internships, encouraging the public to become involved in social action. TOMS uses the iconographic design of its shoes, to promote its cause through a distinct aesthetic. Business models that incorporate giving, do have to sacrifice an aspect of profitability, which may be the reason that more businesses have chosen not to follow this kind of model (Gordon & Mycoskie, 2008). "It is TOMS' hope that as our One for One movement continues to grow, more and more companies will look to incorporate giving into what they do" (TOMS Shoes, 2010). If TOMS wishes to improve on its approach to sustainability, it is important to address the deficiency of online information about its products, which fails to provide specifics of the materials, manufacturing processes, etc. to the public.

SIGG ALUMINUM WATER BOTTLES

Plastics pose a huge challenge to developing sustainable design. It is widely believed that plastic is the best material we have at the moment for storing beverages and many advances are being made in the types of plastics being used (Papanek, 1995). A variety of biodegradable plastics are being developed, but they are more expensive for companies to use than recyclable plastics. This is the reason most companies manufacture their soft-drink bottles using PET, an inexpensive, shatter-resistant, recyclable plastic (polyethylene terephthalate) (Papanek, 1995).

Despite technological innovations in plastics and media campaigns and incentives urging consumers to recycle, vast amounts of recyclable plastic end up in landfills instead of being recycled (Papanek, 1995).

Thousands of tons of... plastic waste, instead of being recycled in the United States, are being shipped to less industrialized countries... where the waste is reprocessed under much less stringent rules for health and environmental safety, or is merely dumped in landfills there (Papanek, 1995).

Approximately 25% of trash in the United States is plastic and it is estimated that a discarded plastic water bottle will last between two to four hundred years (Papanek, 1995). Dr. Allan Hershkowitz, a lead scientist at the U.S. Natural Resources Defense Council, states that over 90% of the environmental impact from plastic water bottles is from the energy and oil used in their manufacturing (SIGG, n.d.). In addition to waste resulting from production, plastic water bottles also pose health concerns. According to Simran Sethi of the Discovery Channel (SIGG, n.d.), disposable PET bottles are meant for one-time use, and refilling them can release harmful toxins into the beverage, especially when the bottle is exposed to heat. Bisphenol A (BPA), a substance present in many hard plastic water bottles, has been deemed a toxic substance by Health Canada (SIGG, n.d.). Many retailers in Canada and worldwide are discontinuing sales of plastic bottles containing BPA (SIGG, n.d.). These facts point to a significant problem in the design of plastic water bottles. Designers must shift to using more sustainable materials in commercially sold beverage containers (Papanek, 1995), but the facts also identify the need for the consumption of less plastic bottles. Many companies are now focusing on designing reusable, aluminum bottles.

Figure 2. Selection of SIGG water bottles (SIGG, n.d.)

SIGG is a Swedish company, founded in 1908, that produces a wide range of aluminum bottles (see figure 2). SIGG bottles are ecologically sound, reusable and ultimately, recyclable, while being

both functional and fashionable (SIGG, n.d.). “For the future we see green and clean, sleek and stylish. Above all, it’s a future of consciousness and commitment” (SIGG, n.d.). With the rising popularity of aluminum water bottles, various companies are now producing them, but many of these companies outsource their manufacturing to Asia, where policies are less strict (SIGG, n.d.). Some cheaply made metal bottles have been recalled due to lead traces in the paint and bottle liners that leach BPA (SIGG, n.d.). SIGG (n.d.) bottles contain a safe, baked on, leach-proof liner. SIGG (n.d.) manufactures its bottles in Switzerland, where it can ensure high quality standards and ethically and environmentally responsible manufacturing processes. Each bottle is produced with 55% renewable energy and minimal waste, with 99% of waste being recyclable (SIGG, n.d.). SIGG appears to effectively use lifecycle assessment in its design process, material considerations, manufacturing processes, finished product and waste. SIGG does not specify how its products are packaged, which is a deficiency in the online information available to the public and an important factor of sustainable design. The company’s website states that it is currently working towards reducing the company’s carbon footprint (SIGG, n.d.), the transportation stage of lifecycle assessment, but this claim remains vague, as no specific details are provided.

SIGG’s marketing to consumers emphasizes the stylish design of their water bottles. The company produces many aesthetically appealing models with a variety of graphic, screen-printed images.

We just love developing new bottle designs every year to stay current with today’s fashions. SIGG produces bottles that are as individual as you are, which means you may need more than one! (SIGG, n.d.).

SIGG produces over 100 new designs every year, aiming to please the tastes a wide customer base (SIGG, n.d.). The company has even commissioned world-renowned fashion designers to design limited edition collections to be auctioned for the benefit of environmental organizations (SIGG, n.d.). While promoting the ideas of ‘using less’ (ie. Using less plastic water bottles), SIGG does encourage customers to purchase multiple water bottles because of their aesthetic appeal. Thus, SIGG

supports using less and purchasing more sustainable products, but not in excess, while also promoting the pleasure that can be derived from their products.

DISCUSSION

Research on TOMS and SIGG reveals similarities and differences when comparing the two companies. Both companies aim to incorporate sustainable practices into their business models and they both attempt to appeal to consumers through design, by offering a range of styles that change periodically. The focus of TOMS’ approach to sustainability is contributing to social sustainability, by using an allotment of the profits for a charitable cause. By encouraging customers to purchase items that are not bought on a regular basis, TOMS gets customers to contribute to a charitable cause but the quantity of the contribution is limited. Unlike TOMS, SIGG focuses on changing peoples’ everyday behaviours, encouraging consumers to decrease usage of disposable bottles and adopt more sustainable behaviours.

Further investigation may delve deeper into the differences between the two companies’ approaches and how these actions can contribute a more sustainable way of life. This paper also implicates future research into the usage of life cycle assessment by businesses and how they can improve sustainable practices. Transparency and publicly available information is another area of potential research, as well as the regulations surrounding it. Can improving transparency encourage businesses to adopt more sustainable practices while helping potential customers make responsible decisions? Another area of further investigation may be assessing the conflicting theories presented in this paper and prioritizing them according to importance in making consumption more sustainable.

CONCLUSION

Design plays an instrumental role in changing consumption behaviours and developing a more sustainable way of life. Our society’s relationship to material goods is complex and understandings of consumer behaviour are varied. When considering how designers can approach sustainable solutions,

one must negotiate a slew of conflicting theories. These theories include: designer's responsibilities to society, consuming less vs. consuming more sustainable goods, policy vs. consumer choice, status-seeking goods vs. identity forming symbolism and fashion vs. long-lasting design. This paper examines TOMS Shoes and SIGG in relation to sustainable design approaches, as they exemplify businesses that are dedicated to creating positive, sustainable change through design.

Understanding oppositional points of view may lead to a more balanced perspective of challenges in sustainable design development. The more designers are informed and knowledgeable about sustainability, the more they can develop effective, holistic, innovative solutions that have the potential to create significant change. Of course, sustainable design solutions are not instantaneous; working towards them is a progressive process of trial and error. With the amount of progress we have made in sustainable design thus far, the potential for future innovations is exciting and inspiring and that is what good design is about.

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